

STONE MONUMENT ENSEMBLES AND THE CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACT

Project ID: 101094822

Funded by
European Union

MILESTONE 1

KICK-OFF MEETING REPORT

the

MILESTONE M1 - KICK-OFF MEETING REPORT

Project acronym:	STECCI
Project full title:	STone monument Ensembles and the Climate Change Impact
Programme:	European Commission, Horizon Europe
Project ID:	101094822
Delivery date:	09/2023
Milestone type	Report
Dissemination level	Public
Leader	UNSA
Authors:	Nusret Dreskovic, Saida Ibragic

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List of abbreviations

- GA – Grant agreement
- WP – Work package
- DEC – Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication
- KoM – Kick-off Meeting
- HE – Horizon Europe

SEPTEMBER 21ST, 2023

DAY 1

Place: Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina

UNSA Rectorate, Obala Kulina bana 7/II, Sarajevo

Meeting type: Hybrid meeting

Chairpersons: Nusret Dreskovic and Saida Ibragic

Session I: Opening and Introduction

The Kick-off meeting started after registration of partners and confirmation of the required quorum according to the Consortium agreement. The event and its first session officially started after welcome speeches of prof. dr. Saida Ibragic (project manager), prof. dr. Rifat Škrijelj (rector of the University of Sarajevo), Ms. Melpomeni Vyzika (project officer, REA) and prof. dr. Nusret Dreskovic (project coordinator). The STECCI first draft unpublished Promo video, created by WP7, was presented to all attendees for the first time (first draft of the promo video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2hCSht8RD3k>).

The chairpersons of the Kick-off meeting were Nusret Dreskovic and Saida Ibragic. The meeting Agenda (Annex 2) was accepted by all project partners.

Saida Ibragic briefly described the project's main objectives and expected outcomes and Nusret Dreskovic presented the University of Sarajevo and its role in the project. The same was done by the following project beneficiaries: HM, UDG, UAA, ZSI, UNSPMF. The IMT representative did not attend the meeting, and he was informed about the outcomes after the meeting.

Session II – Reporting and Financial Planning

Session II started with the presentation on reporting and financial planning by Melpomeni Vyzika and Diana Leblond-Muresan. Special focus was placed on the necessity to work in alignment with the grant agreement (GA) and national laws. Further on, the presentation included sections about requirements such as open access, gender equality plan but also introduced the policy framework, the technical cluster of cultural heritage sustainability, policy feedback activities, amendments, and D&C&E obligations. The reporting guidelines were given by explaining the continuous reporting and periodic reporting. The financial aspects included the presentation of different cost categories, the requirement of the certificate of the financial statements and the flowchart of a sound financial management.

Session III – Management and Dissemination

During session III, management and dissemination were presented as parts of WP1 and WP3. The presentation of each WP included the overview of deliverables, milestones, the timeline and the assignment of WP leaders, task leaders and task members.

The project manager presented the management tree as part of WP1 as follows:

Coordinator: Nusret Dreskovic

Project manager: Saida Ibragic

Financial manager: Nina Begovic

Technical assistant: Ena Hatibovic

As part of the management structure, partners were asked to check and confirm the representatives of their institutions (main representative, vice-representative, administrative and financial representatives).

The consortium agreed on the following WP leaders:

WP1 Nusret Dreskovic

WP2 Nusret Dreskovic

WP3 Gabriela Krist

WP4 Andrew Pace

WP5 Pamela Bartar

WP6 Milica Vukotic

WP7 Snezana Radulovic

WP8 Saida Ibragic

The consortium was introduced to the draft version of the Project management plan (Deliverable 1.1) which includes the scheduling of meetings, voting rights, communication flows, templates and reporting periods. Apart from periodic and final reports, the project beneficiaries are expected to submit three internal reports to facilitate the overall reporting process and to ensure a ensure its timely progress according to the schedule and budget and to mitigate possible risks during the project implementation (as presented in the following table).

Project period	Months	Period covered	Due date to send report to coordinator	Completed and submitted to EC (latest deadline)
Internal Report	M01-M12	01.09.2023 – 31.08.2024	14.09.2024	n/a
EC Periodic Report	M01-M18	01.09.2023 - 28.02.2025	07.03.2025	28.04.2025
Internal Report	M19-M30	01.03.2025 – 28.02.2026	14.03.2026	n/a
EC Periodic Report	M19-M36	01.03.2025 - 30.09.2026	07.09.2026	28.11.2026
Internal Report	M37-M44	01.10.2026 – 30.04.2027	14.05.2027	n/a
Final EC Report	M37-M48	01.10.2026 - 31.08.2027	07.08.2027	29.10.2027

Risk management will be part of the project management plan. The consortium was informed that the proposed members of the quality advisory boards will be contacted to inquire on their previously confirmed interest in the involvement of the STECCI project.

The project manager introduced the WP8 which is related to the ethics requirements. This WP was not part of the original proposal. The project beneficiaries were informed about the main ethics requirements and the WPs which need to pay special attention (population surveys in WP5 and WP6; work with vulnerable persons and minorities in WP5 and WP6; Impact on Cultural Heritage Environment in WP3; Impact of the cultural tourism strategy on remote burial sites in WP5 and WP6). All beneficiaries' representatives will take part in WP8 during the whole project duration.

During the questions and discussion, it was concluded and agreed that each beneficiary needs to update team members in the SyGMa portal, that official corporate emails need to be used for communication purposes and that the coordinating institution needs to send CVs of potential ethics advisor(s) by the end of month. The WP7 was presented by UNSPMF. Snezana Radulovic shared information about the STECCI website, the unpublished first version of promotional video and the draft of the DEC plan. The consortium was asked to review the website and the video and send their suggestions and comments by September 30th, 2023 so that the content can be improved in due time. Beneficiaries were also asked to send media materials with copyrights and contribute by sending blogs to increase the visibility and use of the project website. It was agreed to create a publication schedule at the beginning of the project so that papers can be planned in a timely manner. It was pointed out that UNSPMF will have two new deliverables according to the GA: Policy Brief 1 and Policy Brief 2.

Dinner

The coordinating institution organised a dinner at a restaurant and the project participants interacted and enjoyed their pre-selected meals.

Stone monument ensembles and the climate change impact. Project ID: 101094822

SEPTEMBER 22ND, 2023

DAY 2

Place: Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina

UNSA – Faculty of Science, Zmaja od Bosne 33-35, 71000 Sarajevo

Meeting type: Hybrid meeting

On the second day of the Kick-off meeting UNSA organised a public event to increase the projects visibility and to present its objectives to the wider public. The event was announced on the website <https://steccihorizoneu.com/horizon-europe-opportunities/> 7 days before the event, and the e-mail invitations (Annex 2) were sent to official guest (ambassadors, stakeholders, public agency representatives, local communities, NGOs etc).

There were around 50 attendees from various universities, including STECCI partners, representative from the Embassy of the Republic of Croatia, representatives from the Ministry of Civil Affairs in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Cantonal Institute for the Protection of Monuments of Cultural, Historical and Natural Heritage Sarajevo, Foundation Starobosanski grad Dubrovnik and the Mayor of the of the municipality Ilijaš which is selected as a demo-case location for *in-situ* conservation.

The public event started with a welcome speech by Saida Ibragic, supported by the Promo video, upon which Melpomeni Vyzika presented the Horizon Europe programme and application opportunities. The presentation aimed to encourage the local participation in HE programmes and was particularly useful to the academic staff which attended the event. The UNESCO Head of Office, Antenna Sarajevo, Siniša Šešum was invited to give a speech about stećci as world heritage and during his presentation he welcomed the project's outcomes, which will feed into the UNESCOs work related to the preservation of stećci and expressed support for project's activities, which were further presented by the project coordinator and project manager.

The press releases included daily newspaper Oslobođenje, BH Radio 1 and TV Sarajevo. Within media presentation, several interviews were given by Nusret Dreskovic (UNSA), Siniša Šešum (UNESCO Antenna Sarajevo) and Gordana Vlahovic (UNSPMF) for TV Sarajevo. As for Radio stations, Stefan Simon (SPK), Project Officer Melpomeni Yizika (EC REA), Akif Fazlic (Mayor of the of the municipality Ilijaš) and Nusret Dreskovic successfully presented STECCI project to the broader audience.

Place: Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina

UNSA Rectorate, Obala Kulina bana 7/II, Sarajevo

Meeting type: Hybrid meeting

Chairpersons: Nusret Dreskovic and Saida Ibragic

Session IV - Roles and responsibilities within WP2-WP6

As previous day, all consortium members agreed on the list of experts responsible for the foreseen tasks. Each WP presentation included an overview of tasks, milestones and deliverables.

The WP3 was presented by UAA. Project beneficiaries were asked to send small chips (ca. 2 x 2 cm) of materials from quarries nearby the selected demo-site locations. In addition to that, it was agreed that exposition racks necessary for task 3.4 will be collected after periods of 1 and 2 years, where again some contribution from partners is expected. Within WP3 there was a presentation of SPK whose representative could not attend the first day of the KoM.

The WP4 was presented by HM (online participation).

The WP5 was presented by ZSI (hybrid participation).

The WP6 was presented by UDG.

Administrative aspects of the project were presented by Nina Begovic with special focus on financial reporting, eligible costs, time recording and keeping records. Timesheets were presented by Nusret Dreskovic and the beneficiaries were informed to keep monthly records and send them every 6 months to the coordinator. A separate meeting for project beneficiaries will be organised for administrative and financial matters in the next 2 months.

The STECCI project will use EMDESK as a communication and work tool. The initial data and information was entered by Snezana Radulovic and Edin Hrelja and partners are expected to use EMDESK to report the work progress, expenditures, milestones, deliverables and as a communication tool for online meetings with the possibility of sending group emails. EMDESK was briefly presented by Snezana Radulovic and Nusret Dreskovic. An online meeting for all interested beneficiaries is planned for more detailed instructions.

An outline of the project activities including a meeting schedule, tasks and due dates of milestones and deliverables was given by the project manager.

The meeting minutes were prepared and accepted by all beneficiaries before closing the agenda.

SEPTEMBER 23RD, 2023

DAY 3

Place: Kopošići

Meeting type: Organised trip to the demo-site location (public event)

Participants: representatives from UNSA, UAA, UNSPMF, ZSI, SPK, UDG, UMAS, REA

The event was organised by Edin Bujak with the help of the Foundation Starobosanski grad Dubrovnik who have set up an exhibition and prepared lunch on the site, as well as invited members of the local community. The STECCI beneficiaries first visited the old Bosnian town of Dubrovnik from the medieval times where they received a short lecture on the history of the place and explored the area around the fortress. After that, the STECCI beneficiaries moved to the necropolis of Kopošići where they were welcomed by the Foundation. All project participants went to the necropolis where Edin Bujak gave a short presentation about the history of the stećci on this necropolis. This was a great opportunity for UAA, SPK and UMAS to have a closer look and facilitate their future tasks related to the condition assessment and in-situ conservation.

The main objective of this trip was to provide the project beneficiaries with an insight into the historical, social, traditional background and an opportunity to meet the local community.

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LIST OF PARTICIPANTS

UNSA - University of Sarajevo

HM - Heritage Malta

UAA - Universität für angewandte Kunst Wien

ZSI - Zentrum für soziale Innovation GmbH Wien

SPK - Stiftung Preussischer Kulturbesitz

UDG - Univerzitet Donja Gorica Podgorica

UMAS – Sveučilište u Splitu, Umjetnička akademija

UNSPMF – University of Novi Sad Faculty of Sciences

REA, Project officer

REA, Financial officer

ANNEX 1 AGENDA

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AGENDA

Kick-off meeting
Stone monument ensembles and the climate change
impact STECCI
ID: 101094822 HORIZON-CL2-2022-HERITAGE-01
Type: Hybrid meeting
September 21 - 23, 2023
Sarajevo

Chairpersons:
Prof Nusret Drešković
Prof Saida Ibragić

DAY1UNSA Rectorate, Obala Kulina bana 7/II, Sarajevo

10:00-10:15 REGISTRATION

SESSION I OPENING AND INTRODUCTION

Confirmation of Quorum (2/3 of beneficiaries, from Consortium Agreement)

10:15-10:30 Welcome speeches:

(Rector/Project officer/Project coordinator)

STECCI Promo video

10:30-10:35 Agenda approval, proposed by Chair (voting)

10:35-10:40 STECCI project (Overview, objectives, outcomes)

10:40-10:45 UNSA ppt presentation, including brief overview of role within the STECCI

10:45-10:50 HM ppt presentation, including brief overview of role within the STECCI

10:50-10:55 UDG ppt presentation, including brief overview of role within the STECCI

10:55-11:00 UAA ppt presentation, including brief overview of role within the STECCI
11:00-11:05 SPK ppt presentation, including brief overview of role within the STECCI
11:05-11:10 ZSI ppt presentation, including brief overview of role within the STECCI
11:15-11:20 UMAS ppt presentation, including brief overview of role within the STECCI
11:20-11:25 UNSPMF ppt presentation, including brief overview of role within the STECCI
11:25-11:30 IMT ppt presentation, including brief overview of role within the STECCI
11:30-11:45 *Coffee break*

SESSION II REPORTING AND FINANCIAL PLANNING

11:45-12:45 EU Project officers:

- management
- reporting
- financial reporting

12:45-13:20 Questions and Discussion

13:20-15:00 *Lunch break*

UNSA Rectorate

SESSION III MANAGEMENT AND DISSEMINATION WPs SESSION

15:00-15:45 WP1 Project management and coordination & WP8 (presented by UNSA)

- T1.1 -T1.6 Overview, Deliverables and Milestones
- Appointment of WP1 Leader, T1.1 -T1.6 leaders and team members
- Introducing the Management structure (simple Management tree)
- Introducing the Project Management plan (PMP)
- Intro to Ethics WP (presented by UNSA)
- Introducing the Advisory Board Members

15:45-16:00 Questions and Discussion

16:00-16:45 WP7 Dissemination, exploitation, and communication (presented by UNSPMF)

- T7.1 -T7.8 Overview, Deliverables and Milestones
- Introducing the Dissemination, exploitation, and communication Plan (DEC)
- Introducing the STECCI Project website
- Introducing the STECCI Promo-video Copy rights
- Appointment of WP7 Leader, T7.1 -T7.8 leaders and team members

19:00 **Dinner (organised by UNSA)**

Stone monument ensembles and the climate change impact STECCI ID: 101094822 HORIZON-CL2-2022-HERITAGE-01

DAY2 Faculty of Science, Zmajod Bosne 33 - 35, Sarajevo

- 09:30-10:45 Horizon Europe projects (presentation by Project Officers, public event)
Stećci as world heritage (UNESCO representative, public event)
STECCI project presentation (presentation by UNSA, public event)
- 10:45-11:15 *Coffee break*

UNSA 11:30 REGISTRATION Rectorate Obala Kulina bana 7/II, Sarajevo

SESSION IV ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES WITHIN WP2-WP6

- 11:30-11:45 WP2 Risk and vulnerability assessment based on climate scenarios
(Presented by UNSA Coordinator)
- T2.1 -T2.6 Overview, Deliverables and Milestones
 - Appointment of WP2 Leader, T2.1 -T2.6 leaders and team members
- 11:45-12:00 WP3 Condition, assessment, monitoring and conservation treatments on chosen stećci
(Presented by UAA Coordinator)
- T3.1 -T3.7 Overview, Deliverables and Milestones
 - Appointments of WP3 Leader, T3.1 -T3.7 leaders and team members
- 12:00-12:15 WP4 Digitization (Presented by HM Coordinator)
- T4.1 -T4.4 Overview, Deliverables and Milestones
 - Appointment of WP4 Leader, T4.1 -T4.4 leaders and team members
- 12:15-12:30 WP5 Community-based impact strategies for sustainable stecci ecosystem
(Presented by ZSI coordinator)
- T5.1 -T5.4 Overview, Deliverables and Milestones
 - Appointment of WP5 Leader, T5.1 -T5.4 leaders and team members
- 12:30-12:45 WP6 Economic values (Presented by UDG Coordinator)
- T6.1 -T6.3 Overview, Deliverables and Milestones
 - Appointments of WP6 Leader, T6.1 -T6.3 leaders and team members
- 12:45-13:00 Questions and Discussion
- 13:00-14:30 *Lunch break*
- 14:30-15:00 Administrative aspects of reporting
- 15:00-15:30 Action Plan for the first 6 project months (UNSA)
- 15:30-16:15 Communication and work tools:
- MS Teams platform (presented by UNSA)
 - EMDESK (presented by UNSPMF)

16:15-16:30 Meeting Minutes preparation

16:30-16:40 Adopting the Minutes and Closing the meeting

DAY 3

08:00-13:00 Excursion - Field trip to stecci site Kopošići

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ANNEX 2 STECCI EVENT INVITATION

- PRESENTATION OF HORIZON EUROPE PROJECT OPPORTUNITIES
- STECCI AS WORLD HERITAGE
- PRESENTATION OF THE HORIZON EUROPE PROJECT STONE MONUMENT ENSAMBLES AND THE CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACT (STECI), PROJECT N°: 101094822

22
SEP
2023

Project aim: protection of European cultural heritage from climate change and turning turn the potential of stećak necropoles into new opportunities and resources for economic, social and creative entrepreneurship developments of local communities

HORIZON EUROPE • Melpomeni Vyzika (Project Adviser, REA) | Diana Leblond-Muresan (Financial Officer, REA)

STECI AS WORLD HERITAGE • Siniša Šešum (UNESCO Head of Office, Antenna Office in Sarajevo)

STECI • Nusret Drešković (Project Coordinator) | Saida Ibragić (Project Manager)

<https://steccihorizoneu.com>

EVENT VENUE:

UNIVERSITY OF SARAJEVO
FACULTY OF SCIENCE
ZMAJA OD BOSNE 33-35, SARAJEVO
AMPHITHEATRE (LOW BUILDING)
09:30 - 10:45 (CEST)

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JOIN US ONLINE [HERE](#)

Meeting ID: 829 4175 3798
Passcode: 259306

Consortium:

- University of Sarajevo - Coordinator
- Heritage Malta
- Univerzitet Donja Gorica Podgorica
- Universitaet für angewandte Kunst Wien
- Stiftung Preussischer Kulturbesitz
- Zentrum für soziale Innovation GmbH Wien
- Sveuciliste u Splitu, Umjetnicka akademija
- Faculty of Scences University of Novi Sad
- Institut Mines-Telecom

HORIZON EUROPE

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ANNEX 3 PICTURES OF THE CONSORTIUM

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